

Master thesis proposal

**Shape and size variation of the foramen magnum
in *Homo sapiens*:**

**A broad-scale validation study based on two-
and three-dimensional osteometry
(Working title)**

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Abstract

Most anthropological research requires adequate information about dead individuals, including population affinity and sex. As osteological remains are vulnerable to fragmentation, the application of holistic estimation methods to reconstruct biological parameters are often limited. Therefore, reliable approaches are needed that focus on single bones or morphological features. In this scope, the foramen magnum (FM) in modern humans is of particular interest for the study of sex and population differentiation as it is often well-preserved in forensic or archaeological contexts due to its protected location at the basicranium. The FM has been reported to not be significantly influenced by secular trends, by age-related changes after its developmental completion in early childhood, or by biomechanical forces. Nevertheless, in their work from 2017, Zdilla and colleagues have identified a number of problems associated with previous research on the FM: 1) Most studies only investigate sexual differences on an intrapopulation level; hence, interpopulation variation has rarely been discussed in detail. 2) FM osteometry is limited to only a few linear measurements, which cannot accurately capture the overall shape of the foramen. 3) The application and terminology of the visual classification of FM shape are inconsistent and highly subjective. 4) Lastly, small sample sizes inhibit proper statistical analyses. To address these issues, the proposed project aims to analyze intra- and interpopulation variability of FM size and shape using traditional two-dimensional osteometry as well as three-dimensional landmark-based geometric morphometrics on a large sample of globally distributed populations from different time periods.

1. Introduction and research background

Knowledge about basic biological information, including age-at-death, sex, stature, and population affinity, is crucial to identify unknown individuals from skeletal remains in medicolegal cases, to reconstruct the pathway of humans' morphological evolution, or to analyse patterns and changes in the paleodemography of past groups and societies (Bruzek and Murail, 2006; Cunha and Ubelaker, 2020). Due to the fragile nature of osteological remains, often encountered fragmented in archaeological or forensic contexts, anthropological research is constantly trying to evaluate and develop techniques for different anatomical elements to estimate parameters of the biological profile (Elliott and Collard, 2009; Gapert et al., 2009).

The human cranium has been studied in detail, and a wide range of osteometric and morphological methods have been employed to estimate the sex and population affinities of human skeletal remains. The morphology of the skull has been reported to be the second most useful structure in the human skeleton for biological sex estimation (Bruzek and Murail, 2006), with classification accuracy rates of up to 90% (Williams and Rogers, 2006; Alves et al., 2020). Craniometric sexing methods based on linear measurements reach similar accuracy rates between 80% and 90% (Ramsthaler et al. 2007; Franklin et al. 2006), whereas landmark-based geometric morphometrics (GMM) analyses are reported to correctly differentiate between sexes in 100% for specific cranial landmark configurations (Bigoni et al., 2010). Similarly, predictions of population affiliation using non-metric and metric traits as well as 3D landmark data reach accurate classifications of up to 90% (Hefner, 2009; Navega et al., 2014; Spradley and Jantz, 2016). It is widely known that different cranial structures reflect sexual dimorphism or population differences to various degrees, and some traits are more suitable for sex and population affinity estimations than others (Cunha and Ubelaker, 2020). Furthermore, due to population differences and secular trends, derived methodologies to predict parameters of the biological profile should not be applied to populations other than those included in the reference datasets, as this would lead to systematic biases and lower accuracy rates. The applicability

and reliability of existing methods should therefore be rigorously evaluated and, if possible, adjusted for individual populations (Bruzek and Murail, 2006; Ramsthaler et al., 2007; Elliott and Collard, 2009; Gapert et al., 2009; Bigoni et al. 2010).

A cranial structure that has received much attention in bioarchaeology, forensics, palaeoanthropology, and medicine is the foramen magnum (FM) (Zdilla et al., 2017). The gradual anterior migration of the FM position has been of special interest in the study of the evolution of hominin bipedal locomotion (Landi et al., 2020). In *Homo sapiens*, the FM is located at the basicranial portion of the occipital bone and is traversed by several vital structures, such as the meninges, medulla oblongata, the ascending portion of the spinal accessory nerve, as well as the spinal and vertebral arteries. The FM provides hemodynamic and hydrodynamic functions while also playing an important role in locomotion as it is anterolaterally surrounded by the two atlanto-occipital condyles that, together with the first cervical vertebra, form the craniovertebral joint (Richards and Jabour, 2011; Coumans and Nockels, 2012). The developmental completion of the FM, after which no marked age-related changes happen, normally occurs between the fifth and tenth years of age (Richard and Jabbour, 2010). Despite the fact that the foramen is surrounded by the ligaments and muscles of the neck, which frequently facilitate better preservation relative to more exposed structures (Graw, 2001), the FM is reported to not be noticeably affected by any biomechanical forces (Gapert et al., 2009). Interestingly, several studies have further shown that anatomical differences of the FM have not changed substantially over past generations due to secular trends (Gruber et al., 2009; Zdilla et al., 2017). The overall constitution of FM dimensions seems to be driven mostly by the early ontogenetical development of the cranial base in close relation to the growth patterns of neighboring and passing-through tissues (Richards and Jabour, 2011). Because of the regularly well-preserved condition, the lack of biomechanical effects, no secular changes, and relatively early growth completion, the FM has frequently been described as an ideal structure for the study of intra- and interpopulation variation in humans.

Many previous osteometric and morphological studies have analyzed the wide spectrum of anatomical variation of the FM by solely relying on traditional, linear, or two-dimensional (2D) distance measurements and visual shape categorizations. Based on these variables, significant differences in the mean FM size between sexes could be demonstrated for many populations, whereas females exhibit almost always smaller FMs on average (Gapert et al., 2009; Zdilla et al., 2017). When subjected to regression and discriminant function analysis, classification functions to distinguish between sexes were derived with accuracy rates ranging from around 60% up to 90% (Gapert et al., 2009; Chovalopoulou and Bertsatos, 2017; Abo Al-Atta et al., 2020). Although intrapopulation deviation has been reported for many populations, differences on an interpopulation scale have rarely been discussed.

The predominant use of 2D measurements might partially be related to practical reasons and time constraints, but also to the fact that the FM has regularly been mistaken for a 2D instead of a 3D structure (Toneva et al., 2019). One of the major weaknesses of traditional osteometry is that it fails to adequately collect and account for shape variables, although many studies aim to visually categorize FM shapes. The latter approach has often been validly criticized as being too subjective, consequently leading to a highly skewed perception of FM shape variation (Zdilla et al., 2017). This becomes even more problematic considering the inconsistent use of terminology and shape categorization across many studies (Zdilla et al., 2017). These systematic issues in the design and report of FM research have hardly been acknowledged, while persisting insufficient scientific practice makes it complicated, if not impossible, to conduct cross-study comparisons or further meta-analyses (Zdilla et al., 2017). One possibility to overcome subjectivity in the study of anatomical structures like the FM is the

application of GM analyses using 2D or 3D landmark data (Bookstein, 1991; Mitteroecker and Gunz, 2009). Considering the FM, landmark-based GM approaches have only been tested in two studies. Although limited to either a single population or small sample sizes, they yielded promising results regarding sex estimation (Toneva et al., 2018) and population differentiation (Zdilla et al., 2017).

2. Study aims

This thesis aims to contribute to the discussion on FM shape and size variation through the analysis of a large dataset of globally and temporally distributed modern human populations. Linear osteometry and three-dimensional (3D) landmark-based GM will be applied to estimate patterns of within- and between-population variation while further testing the hypotheses of whether there are intra- and interpopulation differences in shape and size of the adult FM that are independent of biomechanical factors and secular changes. By comparing the results of both approaches and their methodological differences in performance, reliability, and success rates, sets of FM variables most useful to distinguish between sexes and populations will be evaluated. In doing so, the results of this study will provide new insights and perspectives for the estimation of the population affinity and sex of fragmentary remains and the identification of unknown individuals based on this particular anatomical structure.

3. Materials

A sample of around 400 dry human cranial remains from major geographical regions (Africa, Asia, Europe, and the Pacific Ocean; tab. 1) and different time periods (archaeological, historical-colonial, and pre-modern) will be analyzed. All crania were 3D scanned in the anthropological collections in Berlin (Rudolf-Virchow Collection, Felix-von-Luschan Collection, Form Racial Skull Collection, Charité Collection). Permission was granted by responsible holding facilities, respectively, the Berlin State Museums and the Berlin Society for Anthropology, Ethnology, and Prehistory. Crania included adults and did not show indications of pathological or taphonomic alterations affecting the integrity of the FM. Specimens with cranial deformations or other in-vivo, antemortem, or post-mortem modifications were excluded. Populations will be grouped into anthropologically 'meaningful' groups if the number of individuals does not allow for proper statistical analysis (e.g., for Pacific islands and Southeast Asia).

Tab. 1: Number of individuals from the anthropological collections in Berlin.		
Global region / continent	Country	Number of individuals (n)
Africa (total: 89)	Congo	59
	Eritrea	21
	Madagascar	9
Asia (total: 179)	Bengal	10
	Java	34
	Japan	24
	Malaysia	3
	Moluccan islands	9
	Myanmar	9
	Philippines	39
	Sri Lanka	10
	Sulawesi	14
	Thailand	7
	Sumatra	20
Europe (total: 88)	Germany	50
	Greece	17
	Scandinavia	21
Pacific region (total: 44)	Cook-Islands	6
	Fiji Island	8
	Gilbert Island	9
	Marques Islands	6
	Moore Islands	4
	New Caledonia	7
	Tahiti	4
Total (Berlin collections)		400

4. Methods

4.1 Biological sex and age-at-death estimation

As the Berlin Collections mostly host isolated human crania without associated postcranial elements, the estimation of biological sex will be assessed morphoscopically using only the cranium by applying the method of Acsádi and Nemeskéri (1970), modified by Ferembach et al. (1980). The degree of trait expression is weighted using an ordinal scoring system from -2 (hyperfeminine), -1 (feminine), 0 (indifferent), +1 (masculine), and +2 (hypermasculine). The sex will be assigned according to the overall degree of sexualization. In cases where crania either exhibits intermediate trait expressions or a combination of masculine and feminine traits, the individual will be assigned 'indifferent' to not bias further analyses. They will only be included in the interpopulation analyses, whereas intrapopulation examinations will only consider male and female individuals. If associated pelvic bones are present, these will be considered primarily in the sex assessment using the methodological approach for innominate bones (Ferembach et al., 1980; Acsádi and Nemeskéri, 1970). In addition to the morphological approach, statistical sexing methods for specific populations, if available, will be used, and the required craniometric data will be collected with digital sliding (Aickar®, 0.01 mm accuracy) and spreading callipers (iGaging®, 0.01 mm accuracy). Individuals will be considered adults (≥ 20 years of age) when the spheno-occipital synchondrosis is completely obliterated (Schaefer et al. 2009) and the third molar is fully

erupted (Ubelaker, 1989). If available, archival records or previously published information on the ages and sexes of the crania will also be considered.

4.2 3D scanning procedure

Crania were 3D-scanned using an Artec Space Spider structured blue light scanner (Artec 3D Inc., Luxembourg, 0.05 mm accuracy), a turning table, a ring stand, and the Artec Studio 13 Professional software (v13.2.1.13). A minimum of two scans for each cranium were produced in two reverse orientations in order to accurately capture all anatomical details of the FM. After mesh processing in Artec Studio and MeshLab (v2020.12) (Cignoni et al., 2018), the created 3D models were exported as PLY files and saved on a computer for further data collection and analysis.

4.3 Linear measurements

Traditional, linear, or 2D distances (Bräuer, 1988) will be collected using a digital sliding calliper (see above) to measure the maximum anterior-posterior length of the FM (FML) and its largest transversal breadth (FMB). The first is measured from the Basion (ba) to the Opisthion (o), and the latter is described as the most lateral projecting dimension of the FM (Bräuer, 1988) (Fig. 1.1). Both measurements will then be used to calculate the foramen magnum index FMI (Bräuer, 1988), the foramen magnum circularity FMCL (Zdilla et al., 2017), and the foramen magnum area FMA (Radinsky, 1967; Teixeira, 1982). The circumference of the foramen magnum (FMC) will be calculated from the 3D landmark curve (Fig. 1.2).

Fig. 1.1 and 1.2: 3D surface scan of the foramen magnum (basial view) indicating the 2D measurements and fixed 3D landmarks outlined in the text (left: Basion (ba), Opisthion (o), FML (vertical line), FMB (horizontal line), blue dots: 3D landmarks 1 to 4; right: FMA (blue area), FMC (yellow dashed line); not indicated are FMI and FMCL).

Fig. 2: 3D model of the foramen magnum showing roughly equidistant semi-landmarks ($n_{example} = 16$; red dots) along the endocranial margin.

4.4 3D landmark configurations

Two sets of 3D landmark data will be collected from the 3D models and subjected to statistical analysis. For a more direct comparison of 3D shape and form analysis to 2D osteometry, the first 3D landmark configuration will consist of four Bookstein type II landmarks (Bookstein, 1991) that are equal to the craniometric measuring points described before (Basion (LM1), most lateral point left (LM2), Opisthion (LM3), most lateral point right (LM4)) (Fig. 1.1). In addition, a yet-to-be specified number of homologous semi-landmarks will be placed along the endocranial margin of the FM to capture the overall shape of the FM (Fig. 2). To minimize the potential influence of the often protruding and highly variable atlanto-occipital condyles on the FM shape, landmarks will be placed superiorly along a level that represents the line of sight between the anterior- and posterior-most curvature portions of the FM. The R (R Core Team, 2014) package geomorph (Adams and Otárola-Castillo, 2013) will be used to place and slide the landmarks on a pre-defined curve of roughly equidistant surface points. To evaluate the number of semi-landmarks sufficient to accurately capture the shape of the FM, the approach by Watanabe (2018) will be used for two different landmark configurations with 16 and 32 semi-landmarks using a subset of 15 individuals drawn randomly from two populations.

4.5 Intra-observer error

To estimate intra-observer error, 2D measurements and 3D landmark placement of 20 randomly selected skulls will be repeated five times (100 repetitions for each approach) in a time interval of five weeks. Differences between repeated 2D measurements will be estimated using the repeated-measures analysis of variances (ANOVA). Additionally, an extended version of Lin's concordance correlation coefficient for more than two repetitions will be used to examine the degree of intra-observer variability for 2D data (King and Chinchilli, 2001). A repeated-measures ANOVA and intraclass correlation coefficient analysis will be used to detect systematic and random measurement errors in 3D landmark repetitions (Menéndez

2017), while principal component analysis (PCA) will be performed to visually inspect measurement errors.

4.6 Statistical analysis

All statistical analysis will be performed in the open-source statistical computer language and environment R (R Core Team, 2014) using base R functions and, if required, specific packages (e.g., geomorph (Adams and Otárola-Castillo, 2013)). To summarize the metrical characteristics of the FM, descriptive statistics including mean, median, ranges, minimum and maximum values, standard deviations, and standard errors will be reported for all 2D variables of every population as a whole (pooled sexes) and for each sex subgroup individually. Before statistical hypothesis testing, the required assumptions will be evaluated accordingly. If assumptions are not met, non-parametric test equivalents will be used. The significance level alpha will be set to 5% ($\alpha = 0.05$).

For 2D variables, a one-way ANOVA in combination with post-hoc analysis (Tukey's honest significant differences) will be performed to test for mean differences between sexes and among populations. Intrapopulation sex differences will be evaluated with the unpaired Welch two-sample t-test in each population. Finally, the 2D measurements FML and FMB will be subjected to jack-knifed linear discriminant function analysis (LDA) and multiple linear regression analysis (MLRA) to develop models for sex and population estimation.

3D data will be subjected to Generalized Procrustes analysis (GPA) to transform and superimpose all landmarks, removing the influence of scaling, translation, and rotation (Dryden and Marida 1998). Centroid sizes (CS) taken from the GPA will be used in a one-way ANOVA to observe differences between mean CS's for all subgroups. PCA will be performed on the Procrustes landmarks to visually explore patterns of shape differences and morphological variation between groups (Mitteroecker and Gunz, 2009). Sex and population assignment will be estimated using the LDA of the most significant principal components (PCs). Procrustes distances will be calculated to evaluate the shape deviations of males and females from the population average. Goodall's F-test of Procrustes coordinates in combination with a permutation test will be used to test for significant morphological differences between groups (Goodall, 1991; Chovalopoulou et al., 2018). To account for the potential influence of size (i.e., form or allometry), all statistical analyses outlined before will be applied, including log-transformed CS.

5. Expected results

GM analyses are expected to achieve overall higher classification accuracy for sex and population affinity estimations than 2D analysis, as landmark data inherently captures more complete anatomical shape information. As the chosen landmark configuration attempts to exclude the influence of protruding atlanto-occipital condyles on the FM shape analysis, it might give a new perspective on the range of FM shapes that more common, non-standardized visual shape classifications usually fail to account for. As this study analyzes a much larger and geographically more diverse dataset than previous studies (e.g., Zdilla et al., 2017), it is expected to present a broader overview of the global variation of FM dimensions that, furthermore, might reveal better differentiation accuracies between populations. On intrapopulation levels, sexual differences are expected to show significant differences between females and males in FM size variables, consistent with previous studies (e.g., Gapert et al., 2009; Zdilla et al., 2017). Again, 3D data are thought to perform better in sex differentiation.

6. Anticipated time schedule

From March onwards, six to seven months are expected to complete the analyses and thesis manuscript.

Months in 2021	Thesis stage
Summer 2020	Scanning and data collection in Berlin
January	Thesis study design
February	Thesis study design; proposal submission
March	Additional data collection in Berlin
April	Landmark data collection
May	Data handling and analysis
June	Data handling and analysis
July	Manuscript writing
August	Manuscript writing
September	Manuscript submission
October	Thesis defense

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